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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD
FOR ESTIMATION OF DRONEDARONE IN PURE FORM AND
MARKETED PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS****B.Raj Kumar*, Akhila.G, Navya.K, Akshitha.K, Vaishnavi.K, Jagadeesh.P**

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Abstract:

A new, simple, rapid, precise, accurate and reproducible RP-HPLC method for estimation of Dronedarone in bulk form and marketed formulation. Separation of Dronedarone was successfully achieved on a Phenomenex Luna ODS HG-5 RP C18, 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm i.d. column in an isocratic mode of separation utilizing Methanol : Phosphate buffer (0.01M, pH-3.2) in the ratio of 30:70% v/v at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and the detection was carried out at 255nm. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for linearity, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, specificity and robustness. The response was found to be linear in the drug concentration range of 12-28mcg/mL for Dronedarone. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9995 for Dronedarone. The LOD and LOQ for Dronedarone were found to be 5.004 μ g/mL and 15.164 μ g/mL respectively. The proposed method was found to be good percentage recovery for Dronedarone, which indicates that the proposed method is highly accurate. The specificity of the method shows good correlation between retention times of standard solution with the sample solution. Therefore, the proposed method specifically determines the analyte in the sample without interference from excipients of pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: *Dronedarone, RP-HPLC, Accuracy, Precision, Robustness, ICH Guidelines.***Corresponding author:****Dr.B.Raj Kumar,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Dronedarone is a Class III antiarrhythmic drug that works to restore the normal sinus rhythm in patients with paroxysmal or persistent atrial fibrillation. Atrial fibrillation is a common sustained arrhythmia where the treatment primarily focuses on stroke prevention and symptom management¹. It is managed by rate control, rhythm control, prevention of thromboembolic events, and treatment of the underlying disease. Similar to [amiodarone], Dronedarone is a multichannel blocker that works to control rhythm and rate in atrial fibrillation. It meets criteria of all four Vaughan Williams antiarrhythmic drug classes by blocking sodium, potassium, and calcium ion channels and inhibiting β -adrenergic receptors². Dronedarone is a related benzofuran compound to amiodarone but its chemical structure

lacks iodine moieties which are associated with amiodarone-induced thyroid problems. Additionally, the methyl sulfonyl group in its structure renders Dronedarone to be more lipophilic with a shorter half-life than amiodarone. This ultimately leads to reduced tissue accumulation of the drug and decreased risk for organ toxicities, such as thyroid and pulmonary toxicities³. Commonly marketed as Multaq®, Dronedarone was approved by the FDA in July 2009 and Health Canada in August 2009. A safety concern for the risk of drug-induced hepatocellular injury has been issued following marketing of Dronedarone. The IUPAC Name of Dronedarone is 3-(7-amino-3-oxo-1H-indol-2-yl) piperidine-2, 6-dione. The Chemical Structure of Dronedarone is shown in fig-1.

Fig-1: The Chemical Structure of Dronedarone

Only limited methods have been reported in the literature survey³¹⁻³⁵. The aim of the present work was to develop and validate a simple, fast, and reliable isocratic RP-HPLC method for the determination of Dronedarone in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The important features and novelty of the proposed method included simple with sonication of small amount of powder sample at ambient temperature and dilution; short elution time

with good separation eluted prior to Dronedarone; good precision (R.S.D. less than 2%) and high recovery (greater than 98%-102%). Confirmation of the applicability of the developed method was validated according to the International Conference on Harmonisation³⁰ (ICH), to determination of Dronedarone in bulk and marketed pharmaceutical dosage forms.

EXPERIMENTAL:**Instruments Used**

Table-1: Instruments Used

S.No.	Instruments and Glass wares	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.
2	pH meter	Lab India
3	Weighing machine	Sartorius
4	Volumetric flasks	Borosil
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil
7	Digital ultra sonicator	Labman

Chemicals Used:**Table-2: Chemicals Used**

S.No.	Chemical	Brand names
1	Dronedarone	Synpharma Research Lab, Dilsuknagar
2	Water and Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
3	Acetonitrile for HPLC	Merck
4	Ethanol	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
5	DMSO	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
6	DMF	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
7	Orthophosphoric Acid	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai

HPLC Method Development:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol. Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Dronedarone stock solutions⁴ into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Twenty capsules were taken and the average weight was calculated as per the method prescribed in I.P. The weighed tablets were finally powdered and triturated well. A quantity of powder of Dronedarone equivalent to 10mg were transferred to clean and dry 10 ml volumetric flask and 7 ml of HPLC grade⁵ methanol was added and the resulting solution was sonicated for 15 minutes. Make up the volume up to 10 ml with same solvent. Then 1 ml of the above solution was diluted to 10 ml with HPLC grade methanol. One ml (0.1 ml) of the prepared stock solution diluted to 10 ml and was filtered through membrane filter (0.45 μ m) and finally sonicated to degas.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines⁶.

Mobile Phase Optimization:

Initially the mobile phase tried was Methanol and Methanol: Water with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to Methanol and

Phosphate buffer (0.01M, pH-3.2) in proportion 30:70% v/v.

Optimization of Column:

The method⁷ was performed with various C18 columns like, X- bridge column, Xterra, and C18 column. Phenomenex Luna ODS HG-5 RP C18, 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm i.d. was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1.0ml/min flow.

Preparation of Buffer and Mobile Phase:**Preparation of Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate (KH₂PO₄) Buffer (0.01M) (pH-3.2):**

Dissolve 1.36086g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000 ml HPLC water and adjust the pH 3.2 with diluted orthophosphoric acid. Filter and sonicate the solution by vacuum filtration and ultrasonication.

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

Accurately measured 300 ml (30%) of Methanol and 700 ml of Phosphate buffer (70%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Method Validation Parameters**System Suitability**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent⁸. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Dronedarone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD⁹ for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Specificity:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Dronedarone stock

solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Dronedarone sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. Further pipette 0.1ml of Dronedarone above stock solution¹⁰ into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

Inject the three replicate injections of standard and sample solutions and calculate the assay by using formula:

$$\% \text{ ASSAY} = \frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

Linearity and Range:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents¹¹ and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (12ppm of Dronedarone):

Take 0.12ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – II (16ppm of Dronedarone):

Take 0.16ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator¹².

Preparation of Level – III (20ppm of Dronedarone):

Take 0.2ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – IV (24ppm of Dronedarone):

Take 0.24ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – V (28ppm of Dronedarone):

Take 0.28ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Procedure:

Inject each level into the chromatographic system¹³ and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient.

Precision:**Repeatability****Preparation of Dronedarone Product Solution for Precision:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Dronedarone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC¹⁴. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Intermediate Precision:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:**Analyst 1:**

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Analyst 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The

%RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits¹⁵.

Accuracy:

For Preparation of 80% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.08ml of the above Dronedarone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For Preparation of 100% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks¹⁶ add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Dronedarone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For Preparation of 120% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.12ml of the above Dronedarone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

Inject the Three replicate injections of individual concentrations (80%, 100%, 120%) were made under the optimized conditions¹⁷. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for

Dronedarone and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values.

Robustness:

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions are checked for variation of results. .

For preparation of Standard Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dronedarone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Dronedarone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Effect of Variation of Flow Conditions:

The sample was analyzed at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min instead of 1ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 20 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms¹⁸ were recorded.

Effect of Variation of Mobile Phase Organic Composition:

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. Methanol: Phosphate Buffer was taken in the ratio and 35:65, 25:75 instead (30:70), remaining conditions are same. 20 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Method Development:

Wavelength Detection:

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10 μ g/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range¹⁹ from 200-400nm. The UV spectrum of Dronedarone was obtained and the Dronedarone showed absorbance's maxima at 255nm. The UV spectra of drug are follows:

Fig-2: UV Spectrum of Dronedarone

Observation: While scanning the Dronedarone solution we observed the maxima at 255nm. The UV spectrum has been recorded on T60-LAB INDIA make UV – Vis spectrophotometer model UV-2450.

Optimized Chromatographic Method:**Table-3: Optimized Chromatographic Conditions**

Mobile phase	Methanol : Phosphate buffer (0.01M, pH-3.2) = 30:70% v/v
Column	Phenomenex Luna ODS HG-5 RP C ₁₈ , 5µm, 15cmx4.6mm i.d.
Column Temperature	Ambient
Detection Wavelength	255 nm
Flow rate	1.0 ml/ min.
Run time	07 min.
Temperature of Auto sampler	Ambient
Diluent	Mobile Phase
Injection Volume	20µl
Type of Elution	Isocratic

Fig-4: Optimized Chromatographic Condition**Analytical Method Validation:**

Validation²⁰⁻²² was conducted out in accordance with ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines to ensure the analytical method's performance.

System Suitability: System suitability testing is an integral part of many analytical procedures. The tests

are based on the concept that the equipment, electronics, analytical operations and samples to be analyzed constitute an integral system²³ that can be evaluated as such. Following system suitability test parameters were established. The data are shown in Table-4 & 5.

Table-4: Data of System Suitability Test

S.No.	Injection No.	RT	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Injection 1	3.253	284568	7368	1.26
2	Injection 2	3.254	285684	7295	1.25

3	Injection 3	3.215	283659	7346	1.27
4	Injection 4	3.297	284754	7394	1.29
5	Injection 5	3.253	283695	7425	1.25
6	Injection 6	3.213	284578	7385	1.27
Mean			284489.7	7368.833	1.265
S.D			752.5617		
%RSD			0.26453		

Table-5: System Suitability Results for Dronedarone (Flow rate)

S.No.	Parameter	Limit	Result
1	Asymmetry	$T \leq 2$	Dronedarone = 0.12
2	Theoretical plate	$N > 2000$	Dronedarone = 7258
3	Tailing Factor	$(Tf) < 2$	Dronedarone = 1.25

Specificity:

Specificity can be determined by comparing the chromatograms obtained from the drugs with the chromatogram obtained from the blank solution. Blank solution was prepared by mixing the excipients in the mobile phase without drug. Drug solutions were prepared individually and the sample containing three drugs was also prepared. Now these

mixtures were filtered by passing through 0.45 μ membrane filter before the analysis. In this observation no excipient peaks were obtained near the drug in the study run time. This indicates that the proposed method²⁴ was specific. The chromatograms representing the peaks of blank, Dronedarone and the sample containing the three drugs were shown in following figures respectively.

Fig-5: Chromatogram of Blank Solution

Fig-6: Chromatogram of Dronedarone Standard Solution

Observation: In this test method blank, standard solutions were analyzed individually to examine the interference. The above chromatograms show that the active ingredient was well separated from blank and their excipients and there was no interference of blank with the principal peak. Hence the method is specific.

Linearity: To evaluate the linearity, serial dilution of analyte were prepared from the stock solution was

diluted with mobile phase to get a series of concentration ranging from 0-28 μ g/ml for Dronedarone. The prepared solutions were filtered through Whatman filter paper (No.41). From these solutions, 20 μ l injections of each concentration were injected into the HPLC system and chromatographed under the optimized conditions. Calibration curve²⁵ was constructed by plotting the mean peak area (Y-axis) against the concentration (X-axis).

Table-6: Linearity Readings for Dronedarone

CONC. (μ g/ml)	MEAN AUC (n=6)
0	0
12	690316
16	910621
20	1121057
24	1328903
28	1554666

Fig-7: Standard Curve for Dronedarone

Observation: Linearity range was found to be 0-28 μ g/ml for Dronedarone. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9995, the slope was found to be 55283 and intercept was found to be 12871 for Dronedarone.

Accuracy:

Inject the three replicate injections of individual concentrations (80%, 100%, 120%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Dronedarone and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values [26]. Accuracy at different concentrations (80%, 100%, and 120%) was prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Table-7: Accuracy results of Dronedarone

Sample ID	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			%Recovery of Pure drug	Statistical Analysis
	Conc. Found	Conc. Recovered	Peak Area		
S ₁ : 80 %	8	8.064107	458679	99.867	Mean= 100.4113% S.D. = 0.473694346 % R.S.D.= 0.471753
S ₂ : 80 %	8	7.843532	446485	100.637	
S ₃ : 80 %	8	8.19449	465887	100.73	
S ₄ : 100 %	10	9.892661	559767	99.41	Mean= 100.6646667% S.D. = 1.166369295 R.S.D.= 1.158667
S ₅ : 100 %	10	9.978655	564521	100.868	
S ₆ : 100 %	10	10.19623	576549	101.716	
S ₇ : 120 %	12	11.85907	668476	99.878	Mean= 100.4637% S.D. = 0.51154309 % R.S.D. = 0.509181
S ₈ : 120 %	12	12.16785	685546	100.69	
S ₉ : 120 %	12	12.18644	686574	100.823	

Precision: The precision of each method was ascertained separately from the peak areas obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of drug Dronedarone. The percent relative standard deviations²⁷ were calculated for Dronedarone are presented in the Table-8.

i) Repeatability

Obtained Six (6) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Table-8: Repeatability Results of Dronedarone

HPLC Injection Replicates	AUC for Dronedarone
Replicate – 1	285479
Replicate – 2	284571
Replicate – 3	286954
Replicate – 4	283261
Replicate – 5	285964
Replicate – 6	284259
Average	285081.3
Standard Deviation	1318.666
% RSD	0.462558

ii) Intermediate Precision / Ruggedness

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:

Analyst 1: The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Analyst 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Intra Day (Day-1)/Analyst-1:

Table-9: Results of Ruggedness for Dronedarone (Analyst-1)

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Peak Area	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
1	Dronedarone	3.253	284568	7368	1.26
2	Dronedarone	3.254	285684	7295	1.25

3	Dronedarone	3.215	283659	7346	1.27
4	Dronedarone	3.204	286598	7457	1.22
5	Dronedarone	3.202	287965	7635	1.29
6	Dronedarone	3.297	285698	7459	1.28
Mean			285695.3		
Std. Dev.			1508.898		
% RSD			0.528149		

Inter Day (Day -2/Analyst-2):

Table-10: Results of Ruggedness for Dronedarone (Analyst-2)

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Peak Area	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
1	Dronedarone	3.297	294754	7394	1.29
2	Dronedarone	3.253	293695	7425	1.25
3	Dronedarone	3.213	294578	7385	1.27
4	Dronedarone	3.297	296534	7584	1.23
5	Dronedarone	3.210	296571	7745	1.24
6	Dronedarone	3.254	298698	7658	1.25
Mean			295805		
Std. Dev.			1819.334		
% RSD			0.615045		

Robustness: Robustness is defined as the capacity of that method to be unaffected by even small deliberate changes that occur in the method parameters. The evaluation of robustness²⁸ of a method is done by varying the chromatographic parameters such as pH, temperature, flow rate, mobile phase proportions change, ionic strength etc., and determining any possible effect on the results obtained by that method. The results are shown in table-11.

Table-11: Result of Method Robustness Test for Dronedarone

Parameter used for Sample Analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	283261	3.254	7258	1.25
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	315864	3.297	7569	1.29

More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	298542	3.212	7841	1.41
Less organic phase	279856	3.253	7965	1.27
More organic phase	306985	3.215	7458	1.28

LOD: The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample which can be detected, but not quantitated. LOD is a limit test that specifies whether an analyte is above or below a certain value. Signal-to-noise ratio of three-to-one is used to determine LOD.

Observation: The LOD was found to be 1.165µg/ml for Dronedarone.

LOQ: The Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) is defined as the lowest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy under the stated operational conditions of the method. Signal-to-noise ratio of ten-to-one is used to determine LOQ.

Observation: The LOQ was found to be 3.53µg/ml for Dronedarone.

Assay of Marketed Pharmaceutical Dosage form

Twenty tablets/Capsules were taken and the I.P. method was followed to determine the average weight. Finally the weighed tablets are powdered and triturated well by using mortar

Assay % =

$$\frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{DS} \times \frac{DT}{WT} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \text{Avg. Wt} = \text{mg/tab}$$

Where:

AT = Peak Area of drug obtained with test preparation

AS = Peak Area of drug obtained with standard preparation

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg

WT = Weight of sample taken in mg

DS = Dilution of Standard solution

DT = Dilution of sample solution

P = Percentage purity of working standard

The assay²⁹ was performed as explained in the previous chapter. The results which are obtained are following:

Table-12: Recovery Data for Estimation Dronedarone in Dilsave 400mg Tablet

Brand name of Dronedarone	Labelled amount of Drug (mg)	Amount (mg) found by the proposed method (n=3)	Assay %
Dilsave 400mg Tablet (Emcure Pharmaceuticals Ltd)	400mg	399.258 (± 0.079)	99.638% (± 0.047)

Observation: The amount of drug in Dilsave 400mg Tablet was found to be 399.258 (\pm 0.079) mg/tab for Dronedarone & % Purity was 99.638 (\pm 0.047) %.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

To develop a precise, linear, specific & suitable stability indicating RP-HPLC method for analysis of Dronedarone, different chromatographic conditions were applied & the results observed are presented in previous chapters. Isocratic elution is simple, requires only one pump & flat baseline separation for easy and reproducible results. So, it was preferred for the current study over gradient elution. In case of RP-HPLC various columns are available, but here Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C₁₈, 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm i.d. column was preferred because using this column peak shape, resolution and absorbance were good. Mobile phase & diluent for preparation of various samples were finalized after studying the solubility of API in different solvents of our disposal (methanol, acetonitrile, water, 0.1N NaOH, 0.1NHCl). Detection wavelength was selected after scanning the standard solution of drug over 200 to 400nm. From the U.V spectrum of Dronedarone it is evident that most of the HPLC work can be accomplished in the wavelength range of 255 nm conveniently. Further, a flow rate of 1 ml/min & an injection volume of 20 μ l were found to be the best analysis. The result shows the developed method is yet another suitable method for assay which can help in the analysis of Dronedarone in different formulations.

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